

ASSESSING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF EFL LEARNERS

Gulnigor Yuldasheva Otabek qizi

Teacher of English language

Abstract: This article explores how to evaluate intercultural communicative competence of EFL learners. In this article, it is discussed the relationships between linguistic competence and assess students cultural diversity.

Key words: evaluation, intercultural, competence.

Introduction

This is analyzed the idea of communicative competence from numerous factors of view and defines lively bureaucracy and techniques of coaching English. Communication-primarily based totally sports assist in making school room state of affairs greater interactive and offer as an awful lot possibilities for publicity to English as possible. Although there are numerous sports that inspire practising the goal language, the prevailing paper has a tendency to check facts hole sports primarily based totally on communicative language coaching approach. The accurate use of hole duties allows college students to broaden talking capabilities in a secure and personal environment. The results of those forms of responsibilities will constantly be tremendous so long as they're adequate, relevant, authentic, and achievable. The Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) method has end up very famous withinside the place of coaching. It is a method that specializes in verbal exchange and the accomplishment of college students' cappotential to speak. The important intention of coaching a overseas language at faculty is to shape communicative competence of college students.

Literature review

At the flip of the century Milton Bennett humorously mentioned someone who

“speaks a overseas language properly however does now no longer apprehend the social or philosophical content material of that language” as a "fluent fool" [9,16], and Claire Kramsch takes language as cultural semiotic and holds that "so long as subculture acquisition way the cappotential to momentarily see the arena through the eyes of a local speaker or to from time to time behave in methods that agree to local speaker expectations, tradition acquisition have to be a applicable intention of language learning" [22,33]. In order to achieve this aim, CLT recommends coaching English via verbal exchange or with the aid of using the use of it. Furthermore, CLT emphasizes significant verbal exchange instead of the fulfillment of ideal grammar or native-like pronunciation Communicative competence refers back to the cappotential of novices to speak their language understanding effectively. In method the time period «competence» is used as traits of the done degree of the language proficiency. This time period become added with the aid of using N. Chomsky to outline an capacity to meet a few hobby. D. Hymes brought the idea of communicative competence because the capacity to apply the language they may be studying as it should be in a given social encounter. Communicative competence is obtained withinside the method of herbal communique or particularly prepared education together with numerous components, which include language competence, challenge competence, linguistic competence and pragmatic competence It must be cited that presentingone's personal thoughts, mainly in a overseas language, is a as a substitute complex procedure, each from a linguistic and mental factor of view. It has been confirmed that one of the important motives for the concern of college students to talk to strangers in a overseas language is their loss of conversation talents. The loss of motivation withinside the speech pastime of college students, the mechanical overall performance of speech movements deprives the speaker of such traits as communique, hobby, cognizance and thereby prevents the amassed talents from going into herbal speech conversation. This is in part because of the truth that the mastery of speech abilities, requiring extra intellectual hobby, creativity, is postponed to a speech Also, it is said that: “Thus,growing the intercultural measurement in language coaching includes recognising that the pursuits are: to offer rookies

intercultural competence in addition to linguistic competence; to put together them for interplay with humans of different cultures; to permit them to recognize and be given human beings from different cultures as people with different distinctive perspectives, values and behaviors; and to assist them to look that such interplay is an enriching experience” [10,10].

Methodology

At the equal time, it's miles important to create advantageous situations for the lively and loose participation of the man or woman in sports: -Students get the possibility to freely explicit their mind and emotions withinside the manner of communicate;- Each player in organization verbal exchange stays withinside the awareness of interest of the rest;- Self-expression of the person will become extra crucial than the demonstration of linguistic knowledge;- Even contradictory, paradoxical judgments are encouraged, however attesting to the independence of college students, approximately their energetic position;- Participants in verbal exchange sense secure from criticism, prosecution for errors and punishment;- The use of linguistic fabric is concern to the project of an person speech concept;-The linguistic fabric corresponds to the speech-wondering skills of the speaker;- Relationships are constructed on empathy and knowledge of the stories of others.In this case, speech mistakes ought to be taken into consideration now no longer best viable, however additionally normal. The above situations are essential whilst coaching an overseas language.An vital position withinside the implementation of non-conventional techniques is performed with the aid of using the informative competence of college students, which includes:-Informational "frames";-Established knowledge;- Linguistic photograph of the world (language illustration of the world) in its overseas language form;- Background knowledge;- General outlook.This is an crucial prerequisite for enticing college students in verbal exchange. The silence of the scholar withinside the lesson is frequently defined via way of means of the truth that he does now no longer recognise the situation of the conversation, does now no longer have a private courting to the hassle beneath discussion, isn't acquainted with viable methods of behavior, even though he has discovered vocabulary with grammar

Richards and Rogers and Richards argued that communicative technique operations are unlimited.

Conclusion and Suggestion

These sports help beginners gain the curriculum's communicative objectives, in addition to contain college students withinside the system of verbal exchange including interaction, sharing of statistics and that means this is negotiated. Pair paintings and organization paintings seemed because the number one items for verbal exchange language coaching withinside the framework of college operations. There are many getting to know techniques or sports which might be normally decided on for reinforcing language studying. Communication-orientated coaching of the English language may be achieved the use of the "statistics hole" tasks. An records-hole assignment is a method where in freshmen are lacking the wished records to finish a undertaking or clear up a hassle, and that they need.

Reference:

1. Nadene Nichole Vevea. Intercultural Communication Theory: Integrating Academic and Practical Perspectives. -2011. -P.13.
2. Nun. R. Redefining Communicative Competence for International and Local Communities.” Journal of English as an International. -2007. P.43.
3. Oskamp. Stuart. Attitude and Opinions. Prentice- Hall. -1977. P.19
4. Poole. M.S and Van De Ven. A.H. Using Paradox to Build Management and Organization Theories. -1989. -P.563
5. Rathje. S. Intercultural Competence: The Status and Future of a Controversial Concept. -2017. -P.255
6. Ruben. B.D. Assessing Communication Competency for Intercultural Adaptation. -1976. -P.339
7. Sabri Thabit Ahmed. Communicative Competence in English as a Foreign Language: Its Meaning. -2018. -P.303
8. Samovar. L. A. Porte. R. E., and McDaniel. E. R. Communication between Cultures (9th ed.). Boston, Mass: Wadsworth/Cengage Learning. -2015. P.243.

9. Savignon. S. J. Communicative competence: Theory and classroom practice (2nd ed.).-1997.P.114
10. Shaules. J. Deep Culture: The hidden challenges of global living.2007.P.98.
11. Svetlana Dmitrova-Gyuzelova. Developing intercultural communicative competence-two sides of the coin. ERL Journal Vol .2(2) .2019. - P. 16.
12. Ting-Toomey. Communicating Across Cultures.-1999.-P.113.
13. Van Compernelle. R. A. Concept appropriation and the emergence of L2 sociostylistic variation. Language Teaching Research.-2013.P.358
14. Wodak. R. Introduction: Some Important Issues in The Research of Gender and Discourse.1997.-P.13.